

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: REHNBERG****FIRST NAME: STEPHEN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCTh****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 MSO Version 2310 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to Turabian, how does research-based writing differ from other kinds of persuasive writing?
 - Research-based writing simply states the facts and does not attempt to persuade the readers to a particular point of view.
 - Research-based writing differs from other kinds of persuasive writing: it must rely on shared facts that readers accept as truths independent of your feelings and beliefs.¹**
 - Research-based writing is synonymous with persuasive writing; both writing forms attempt to influence the readers to a particular point of view.

1. Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 6.

- Research-based writing is neutral and does not argue a particular point of view as does persuasive writing.
2. In her discourse on “Writing a History Paper: *Formulating a Research Question*,” Kristin Poling listed seven questions that share a common nature and that should be avoided by the research writer. What types of questions does Poling say are to be avoided?
- The research writer wants to avoid those questions that are not *empirically resolvable*.**²
- The research writer wants to avoid those questions that are ambiguous.
- The research writer wants to avoid those questions that are overly controversial.
- The research writer wants to avoid those questions to which the answers are philosophical in nature.
3. According to Turabian, exact quotations are recorded for four purposes. Which of the following **is not** one of the four purposes?
- The words are from an authority you plan to rely on or challenge.
- The words express a claim that you disagree with.
- The words, although not original or compelling, can frame the rest of your discussion.**³

2. Kristin Poling, “Writing a History Paper Formulating a Research Question,” September 2, 2010, https://history.fas.harvard.edu/files/history/files/research_question.pdf?m=1459176775.

3. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 44.

- The quoted words are evidence that backs up your reasons.
4. According to Turabian, when is a warrant added to your argument?
- When you think a reader might reject your claim not because a reason supporting it is factually wrong or is based on insufficient evidence, but because it seems *irrelevant* and so doesn't count as research at all.⁴**
- When your argument is weak.
- When your claim is philosophical or theological in nature.
- When the authority cited in your argument is controversial.
5. According to Dr. Philip Adu, what is the difference between a quantitative research project and a qualitative research project?
- In a quantitative research project, you make observations to test a theory, whereas, in a qualitative research project, you make observations to develop a theory.⁵**
- In a quantitative research project, you collect and analyze data, whereas, in a qualitative research project, you interview people.
- In a quantitative research project, you make observations to develop a theory, whereas, in a qualitative research project, you make observations to test a theory.

4. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 58.

5. Philip Adu, "Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter," YouTube, 2016, 0.00:32.

- There is no difference. In both quantitative research projects and qualitative research projects you collect data to prove a theory. The difference is in the type of data collected.
6. Madeleine Young from the University of Melbourne suggests that a research question should (1) focus on a clear, specific, and significant problem or puzzle, (2) Be shaped in a way that allows it to be answered with different research results, and (3) Be revisited frequently in the research process. According to Philip Adu, if the research question is qualitative in nature, then two additional attributes should be present; namely,
- The research question should be (1) closed-ended and (2) exploratory.
 - The research question should be (1) open-ended and (2) empirically resolvable.
 - The research question should be (1) closed-ended and (2) empirically resolvable
 - The research question should be (1) open-ended and (2) exploratory.**⁶
7. What is the purpose of the English Style Guide promulgated by the European Commission?
- The overriding goal and purpose of the English Style Guide is to encourage European Union members to adopt English as their primary language for correspondence between members.

6. Adu, "Conducting Qualitative Research," 0.10:06 to 0:10:42.

- The overriding goal and purpose of the English Style Guide is to facilitate and encourage the writing of clear and reader-friendly American English among the members of the European Union.
 - The overriding goal and purpose of the English Style Guide is to facilitate and encourage the writing of clear and reader-friendly English among the European Union members.⁷**
 - The overriding goal and purpose of the English Style Guide is to instill a rigorous set of rules for all correspondence among members of the European Union.
8. The European Commission English Style Guide has a special limitation on the use of the word “shall.” What is that limitation?
- Legal protocols within the European Union do not allow the use of “shall” outside enacting terms of legislation when either “must” or “is required to” is implied.⁸**
 - Legal protocols within the European Union require that the word “shall” can only be used outside enacting terms of legislation.
 - Legal protocols within the European Union require that the word “shall” can only be used in legislation that is between two European Member nations.
 - Legal protocols within the European Union require that the word “shall” cannot be used in treaties between European Union members.

7. European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8 ed. (European Union, 2021), 4.

8. European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 60.

9. According to Philip Adu, there are five main research approaches for a qualitative research project. Which of the following **is not** an approach for a qualitative research project?

- Phenomenological approach.
- Double-blind study approach.**⁹
- Grounded theory approach.
- Ethnography.

10. According to Dr. James P. Sampson, Jr., what is the purpose of the Discussion Chapter in the dissertation?

- The Discussion Chapter provides the reader with the data needed to reach his or her own tentative answer to the research questions posed in the dissertation research.
- The Discussion Chapter summarizes the data and shows how the data proves each hypothesis.
- The Discussion Chapter provides an interpretation of the findings of the dissertation research within the context of the literature review, using key citations from the review of the literature chapter to support the interpretation for each hypothesis.**¹⁰
- The Discussion Chapter provides the reader with a detailed description of the soundness of the method that was used in the research to prove each hypothesis.

9. Adu," Conducting Qualitative Research," 0.12:55.

10. James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 56.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adu, Philip. "Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter." YouTube, 2016.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. European Union, 2021.

Poling, Kristin. "Writing a History Paper Formulating a Research Question," September 2, 2010.
https://history.fas.harvard.edu/files/history/files/research_question.pdf?m=1459176775.

Sampson Jr., James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.